

Effects of planting arrangement on the occurrence of tungro virus infection in mixtures of resistant and susceptible varieties

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The application of variety mixtures has been shown to be an effective strategy to manage various fungal diseases of cereals (Mundt 2002). Nevertheless, few attempts have been made to examine the effects of variety mixtures on viral diseases in cereals. Rice tungro disease (RTD) is caused by the interaction between rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) and rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), both of which are transmitted by green leafhoppers (GLH) (Hibino et al 1990). To evaluate the efficacy of variety mixtures in the management of RTD, we examined the occurrence of tungro virus infection in confined settings simulating the mix-planting of RTD-susceptible IR64 and RTD-resistant Matatag 9 (IR73885-1-4-3-2-1-6) (Khush et al 2004).

To assess the virus transmission capability of GLH (*Nephotettix virescens*) for tungro viruses in the setting of a variety mixture, the incidence of tungro virus infection in IR64 and Matatag 9 serially inoculated with viruliferous GLH was examined (see figure). Single six-day-old seedlings of both varieties were infested with one viruliferous GLH for 24 h. The viruliferous GLH were then transferred daily to other seedlings for 3 d in the sequences shown in the figure. The rates of tungro virus infection were evaluated at 21 d after inoculation (DAI) by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. The con-

secutive transmission of RTBV to IR64 by GLH was observed for 4 d, although the infection rate was only about 1% on the fourth day (see figure, A). However, the transmission of RTSV to IR64 was observed for only 2 d. Meanwhile, both viruses were detected only in the first plants of the serial transmission through Matatag 9 (see figure, B). In serial transmissions alternating between IR64 and Matatag 9 (see figure, C and D), the transmission capability of GLH was retained only when they were transferred from Matatag 9 to IR64. These findings suggest

that the transmission of tungro viruses by GLH was adversely affected when GLH were fed on Matatag 9.

To examine whether the proportion and distribution of Matatag 9 in the mixtures affect RTD occurrence, the rates of virus infection in variety mixtures established by seed mix and interplanting were compared. For the seed mix, seeds of Matatag 9 and IR64 were premixed in ratios specified in the table and sown in a plastic tray (49 cm × 37 cm × 12.5 cm) with 16 columns, 25 seeds per column. For the interplanting, the

Serial transmission of tungro viruses by GLH (*Nephotettix virescens*) on IR64 and Matatag 9. Single plants of IR64 and Matatag 9 (M9) were inoculated with one viruliferous GLH for 24 h. The viruliferous GLH were transferred daily to other plants in the sequences as depicted in A-D. The rates of infection with RTSV (S) and RTBV (B) and those of simultaneous infection with RTBV and RTSV (BS) were evaluated at 21 DAI. The rates of infection were based on results from 40 plants with three replications.

planting columns consisting of either of the two varieties were arranged in trays according to specified ratios. Ten-day-old seedlings were mass-inoculated with 3 or 10 viruliferous GLH per plant for 4 h. The rates of virus infection were evaluated at 21 DAI and normalized by the corresponding rates in the monoculture of IR64 for proper comparison. The experiment was set up using a split-plot design with three replications.

In general, the relative rates of tungro virus infection decreased significantly as the proportions of Matatag 9 in the mixtures increased, regardless of mixing method (see table). For the 75%:25% and the 25%:75% mixtures of IR64 and Matatag 9 inoculated with three viruliferous GLH per plant, the relative rates of infection with either tungro virus in the mixtures by seed mix were significantly lower than those in the corresponding mixtures by interplanting. Significant differences in the relative rate of simultaneous infection with RTBV and RTSV (RTBV+RTSV infection) were also observed between the mixtures by seed mix and the corresponding mixtures by interplanting inoculated with 10 GLH per plant. The relative rates of RTSV infection and those of RTBV+RTSV infection in the mixtures by seed mix inoculated with three GLH per plant were apparently lower than the actual ratios of IR64 in the mixtures, thus demonstrating the effectiveness of the seed mix in suppressing RTSV infection. The results presented here collectively indicate that the mixtures of a susceptible and a resistant variety, especially those by seed mix, could be applied to manage RTD in fields under moderate disease pressure.

References

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Relative <i>rt</i>	GLH per plant ^c (no.)	Variety ratio ^b	Rate of infection with RTBV + RTSV (%) ^e		Rate of infection with RTBV (%)		Rate of infection with RTSV (%)				
			Seed mix	Interplanting	Difference ^d	Seed mix	Interplanting	Difference	Seed mix	Interplanting	Difference
3		100% R	2.0 ae	2.0 a	0.0 ns	14.9 a	17.3 a	2.5 ns	5.9 a	4.8 a	1.1 ns
		75% R:25% S	17.3 b	34.3 b	17.1*	31.5 b	49.6 b	18.0**	19.5 b	36.0 b	16.5*
		50% R:50% S	39.4 c	51.0 c	11.6 ns	51.4 c	59.9 b	8.5 ns	42.0 c	52.2 c	10.1 ns
		25% R:75% S	66.4 d	82.8 d	16.4*	69.3 d	84.6 c	15.3*	67.5 d	82.8 d	15.3*
		100% S	100.0 e	100.0 e	0.0 ns	100.0 e	100.0 d	0.0 ns	100.0 e	100.0 e	0.0 ns
10		100% R	15.7 a	14.7 a	0.9 ns	83.4 a	74.1 a	9.3 ns	16.8 a	15.2 a	1.6 ns
		75% R:25% S	29.8 ab	43.1 ab	13.3*	88.8 a	94.7 a	5.9 ns	30.2 ab	41.2 b	11.0 ns
		50% R:50% S	49.0 b	60.2 b	11.2*	93.1 a	100.3 a	7.2 ns	47.6 b	57.1 b	9.5 ns
		25% R:75% S	89.8 c	101.2 c	11.5*	98.8 a	106.7 a	7.9 ns	86.7 c	93.6 c	6.8 ns
		100% S	100.0 c	100.0 c	0.0 ns	100.0 a	100.0 a	0.0 ns	100.0 c	100.0 c	0.0 ns

^aApproximate number of RTBV/RTSV-viruliferous GLH per plant to mass-inoculate a variety mixture. ^bR: Matatag 9, S: IR64. ^cRate of infection in each treatment was normalized by the corresponding rate in the monoculture of IR64 (100% S). ^dDifference in the relative rate of infection between a variety mixture established by seed mix and that by interplanting. ^e** = difference significant at 1% level, * = significant at 5% level, ns = not significant. ^fMeans for infection rate in variety mixtures inoculated with the same number of GLH followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by LSD test.